

O‘ZGARUVCHAN KUCH TA’SIRIDAGI ELASTIK-PLASTIK NAZARIYASI ASOSIDA BALKANING SOF EGILISHINI MUVOZANAT TENGLAMASI VA ALGORITMINI ISHLAB CHIQISH

Ismoilov Shohimardon Muhammadjonovich PhD

Namangan muhandislik-qurilish instituti, Namangan shahri.

shohsoft@gmail.com

Abdujalilov Sodikjon Muhammadamin o‘g‘li o‘qituvchi

Namangan muhandislik-qurilish instituti, Namangan shahri.

sodiq.abdujalilov1992@gmail.com

Ismoilov Ahror Muxamadibragimovich o‘qituvchi

Namangan muhandislik-qurilish instituti, Namangan shahri.

aismoilov802@gmail.com

ANNOTATSIYA

Bino va inshootlar qurilishida foydalaniladigan konstruksion materiallarning kuchlanganlik-deformasiyalanganlik holatlarini o‘rganish, ularning turli yo‘nalish va o‘zgaruvchan yuklanishlar ta’siridagi elastik-plastik deformatsiyalanish holatlarini sonli yoki eksperimental tadqiq etish-loyihalash institutlarida hal etilishi lozim bo‘lgan eng muxim masalalardan biridir. Mazkur ish aynan ushbu vazifani hal etishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: chegaraviy masala, elastinka-plastinka, eksperiment, kuch, bino inshootlar.

Chegaraviy masalani yechishda o‘zgaruvchan kuch ta’siridagi elastik-plastik nazariya asosida balkaning sof egilishini muvozanat tenglamasi va algoritmini ishlab chiqish, masalaning matematik modelini qurish, chekli ayirmalar usuli haqida asosiy tushunchalar, chegaraviy masalani chekli ayirmalar va haydash usullari yordamida yechish algoritmlari keltirilgan.

Biz dissertatsiya ishida asosan balkaning sof egilishini aniqlovchi elastik-plastik nazariyalarigi asosan, o‘zgaruvchan kuch ta’siridagi algoritmini quramiz.

O‘zgaruvchan kuch ta’siridagi elastik-plastik V.V.Moskvitin nazariyasi va T.Bo‘riyevning qo‘rsatmalari umumlashgan nazariyalariga asoslangan masalani algoritmini aniqlaymiz.

Masalaning matematik modelini qurish

Yuqorida qo'yilgan masalani matematik modelini qurish uchun Lagranjning variasion prinsipiga asosan muvozanat tenglamasidan foydalanamiz:

$$\delta(-\Pi + A) = -\delta\Pi + \delta A \quad (1)$$

Bu yerda

$$\delta\Pi = \int_V \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_{1i}^{(k)} \cdot \varepsilon_{1i}^{(k)} dV = \int_V \sigma_{11}^{(k)} \delta\varepsilon_{11}^{(k)} \quad (2)$$

$$\delta A = \int_V P_1 \delta V_1 dV + \int_S q_1 dV_1 ds \Big|_x \quad (3)$$

Ifoda potensial energiyani (2) ni tashqi kuchlarni variatsiyasi (3) ni muvozanat tenglamasi (1) ga qo'yib, integrallab, variatsalab quyidagicha, belgilashlar kiritib quyidagi ko'rinishga ega bo'lamiz.

$$\delta\Pi = \int_V \sigma_{11}^{(k)} \delta\varepsilon_{11}^{(k)} dV = 2G \int \int \int_{x y z} \left[(1 - \omega^{(k)}) \varepsilon_{11}^{(k)} - \omega^{(k)} \varepsilon_{11}^{0(k-1)} + \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \omega^{0(k-m)} \left(\varepsilon_{11}^{0(k-m)} - \varepsilon_{11}^{0(k-m-1)} \right) \right] \delta\varepsilon_{11}^{(k)} dz dy dx$$

yoki

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\Pi &= \int_V \sigma_{11}^{(k)} \delta\varepsilon_{11}^{(k)} dV = 2G \int \int \int_{x y z} \left[(1 - \omega^{(k)}) Z \cdot \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} - \omega^{(k)} \cdot Z \frac{d^2 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^2} + \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \omega^{0(k-m)} \left(Z \cdot \frac{d^2 \omega^{0(k-m)}}{dx^2} - Z \cdot \frac{d^2 \omega^{0(k-m-1)}}{dx^2} \right) \right] \delta \left(Z \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} \right) dz dy dx = \\ &= 2G \int_x \left[\left(\int \int_{y z} Z^2 (1 - \omega^{(k)}) dz dy \right) \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} \cdot \delta \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} dx - 2G \int_x \left[\int \int_{y z} Z^2 \omega^{(k)} dz dy \right] \cdot \frac{d^2 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^2} \delta \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} dx + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 2G \int_x \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \left[\int \int_{y z} Z \omega^{0(k-m)} \left(\frac{d^2 W^{0(k-m)}}{dx^2} - \frac{d^2 W^{0(k-m-1)}}{dx^2} \right) \delta \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} \right] dx \right] \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} M_y &= \int_y \int_Z \dot{z} d\dot{z} dy & M_y^{\omega(k)} &= \int_y \int_Z \dot{z} \omega^{(k)} d\dot{z} dy \\ M_y^{0(k-m)} &= \int_y \int_Z \sum_{zm=1}^{k-1} \dot{z} \omega^{0(k-m)} d\dot{z} dy \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

(4) formulaga (5) ni olib kelib qo‘ysak quydagicha ko‘rinishga keladi

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \Pi &= 2G \int_x \left[\left(M_y - M_y^{\omega(k)} \right) \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} \delta \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} - M_y^{\omega(k)} \cdot \frac{d^2 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^2} \cdot \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} + \right. \\ &+ \left. M_y^{0(k-m)} \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \left(\frac{d^2 W^{0(k-m)}}{dx^2} - \frac{d^2 W^{0(k-m-1)}}{dx^2} \right) \delta \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} \right] dx \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Oxirgi (6) formuladagi variatsiya belgisi ostidagi hosilani (ikkinchi tartibliga) o‘tkazib, yo‘qotish uchun bo‘laklab integrallab, o‘rniga q o‘yib, quyidagi ko‘rinishga keltiriladi.

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \Pi &= 2G \left(M_y - M_y^{\omega(k)} \right) \left\{ \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x - \int_x \frac{d^3 W^{(k)}}{dx^3} \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} dx \right\} - \\ &- 2GM_y^{\omega(k)} \left\{ \frac{d^2 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^2} \cdot \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x - \int_x \frac{d^3 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^3} \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} dx \right\} + \\ &+ 2GM_y^{0(k-m)} \left\{ \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \left[\left(\frac{d^2 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^2} - \frac{d^2 W^{0(k-m-1)}}{dx^2} \right) \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \right] \Big|_x - \right. \\ &\left. - \int_x \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \left(\frac{d^3 W^{0(k-m)}}{dx^3} - \frac{d^3 W^{0(k-m-1)}}{dx^3} \right) \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} dx \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

(7) formuladan variatsiya ostidagi ifodani yana bo‘laklab integrallaymiz va quyidagi ko‘rinishga keltirib olamiz:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta \Pi = & 2G \left(M_y - M_y^{\omega(k)} \right) \left\{ \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x - \frac{d^3 W^{(k)}}{dx^3} \delta W^{(k)} \Big|_x \cdot \int_x \frac{d^4 W^{(k)}}{dx^4} \delta W^{(k)} dx - \right. \\
 & - 2GM_y^{\omega(k)} \left[\frac{d^2 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^2} \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx^2} \Big|_x - \frac{d^3 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^3} \delta W^{(k)} \Big|_x + \int_x \frac{d^4 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^4} \delta W^{(k)} dx \right] + \\
 & + 2GM_y^{0(k-m)} \left\{ \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \left[\left(\frac{d^2 W^{0(k-m)}}{dx^2} - \frac{d^2 W^{0(k-m-1)}}{dx^2} \right) \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - \left(\frac{d^3 W^{0(k-m)}}{dx^3} - \frac{d^3 W^{0(k-m-1)}}{dx^3} \right) \delta W^{(k)} \Big|_x \right] + \int_x \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \left(\frac{d^4 W^{0(k-m)}}{dx^4} - \frac{d^4 W^{0(k-m-1)}}{dx^4} \right) \delta W^{(k)} dx; \right. \tag{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

Tashqi kuch variyasiyasini xisoblashimiz kerak bo‘ladi buning uchun:

(2) formuladan

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta A = & \int_v p \delta Z \frac{dW}{dx} dv + \int_s q_1 \delta v_1 ds \Big|_x + \int_x \left(\int_F \int_Z \mathbf{q} \delta \mathbf{z} dy \right) \cdot \delta \frac{W}{dx} dx \\
 \int_y \int_Z \mathbf{q} \delta \mathbf{z} dy \delta \frac{dW}{dx} \Big|_x = & Q^T \int_x \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} dx + Q^\Gamma \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} = \\
 = & \int_x Q^T \delta W^{(k)} + Q^\Gamma \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x \tag{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

Bu yerda

$$Q^T = \int_y \int_Z \mathbf{z} \delta \mathbf{z} dy, \quad Q^\Gamma = \int_y \int_Z \mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{z} \delta \mathbf{z} dy$$

(10), (9) formulalarni (1) ga qo‘ysak quyidagi ko‘rinishga keladi:

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\delta \Pi + \delta A = & \left[2G \left(M_y - M_y^{\omega(k)} \right) \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} - Q^\Gamma \right] \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x + \\
 + 2G \left(M_y - M_y^{\omega(k)} \right) \frac{d^3 W^{(k)}}{dx^3} \cdot dW^{(k)} \Big|_x - & \int_x \left(2G \left(M_y - M_y^{\omega(k)} \right) \frac{d^4 W^{(k)}}{dx^4} - Q^T \right) \delta W^{(k)} dx = \\
 = -2GM_y^{(k)} \left[\frac{d^2 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^2} \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x + \frac{d^3 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^3} \delta W^{(k)} \Big|_x - \right. \\
 \left. - \int_x \frac{d^4 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^4} dx \delta W^{(k)} \right] - & 2GM_y^{0(k-m)} \int_x \left\{ \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \left(\frac{d^2 W^{0(k-m)}}{dx^2} - \frac{d^2 W^{0(k-m-1)}}{dx^2} \right) \cdot dx \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x + \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \left(\frac{d^3 W^{(k-m)}}{dx^3} - \frac{d^3 W^{(k-m-1)}}{dx^3} \right) \delta W^{(k)} \Big|_x - \int_x \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \left(\frac{d^4 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^4} - \frac{d^4 W^{0(k-m-1)}}{dx^4} \right) \delta W^{(k)} dx \quad (11)$$

Muvozanat tenglamasi va unga mos chegaraviy shartlardan keltirib quyidagicha chiqaramiz.

Yuqoridagi tenglamalardan foydalanib akademik T.Bo‘riyevni umumlashgan algoritmlariga asosan [6] quyidagicha yozib olishimiz mumkin bo‘ladi:

$$2G \left[- \left(M_y - M_y^{\omega(k)} \right) \frac{d^4 W^{(k)}}{dx^4} \delta W^{(k)} = Q^T \delta W^{(k)} + A^{0(k-1)} + B^{0(k-m)} \right] \quad (12)$$

$$2G \left(M_y - M_y^{\omega(k)} \right) \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x + 2G \left(M_y - M_y^{\omega(k)} \right) \frac{d^3 W}{dx^3} \delta W^{(k)} \Big|_x = \quad (13)$$

$$= Q^T \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x + A^{0\Gamma(k-1)} + B^{0\Gamma(k-m)}$$

bu yerda

$$A^{0(k-1)} = -2GM_y^{(k)} \int_x \left[\frac{d^2 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^2} \right] \delta W^{(k)} dx$$

$$B^{0(k-m)} = 2GM^{0(k-1)} \int_x \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \left(\frac{d^4 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^4} - \frac{d^4 W^{0(k-m-1)}}{dx^4} \right) \delta W^{(k)} dx$$

$$A^{0\Gamma(k-1)} = 2GM_y^{(k)} \left[\frac{d^2 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^2} \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x + \left[\frac{d^3 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^3} \delta W^{(k)} \Big|_x \right] \right] \quad (14)$$

$$B^{0\omega(k-m)} = -2GM_y^{0(k-m)} \left\{ \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \left(\frac{d^2 W^{0(k-1)}}{dx^2} - \frac{d^2 W^{0(k-m-1)}}{dx^2} \right) \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x + \right.$$

$$\left. + \left(\frac{d^3 W^{0(k-m)}}{dx^3} - \frac{d^3 W^{0(k-m-1)}}{dx^3} \right) \delta W^{(k)} \Big|_x \right\};$$

(13) tenglamada balkaning sof egilishini elastik-plastik o‘zgaruvchan kuchlarning ta’siridagi muvozanat tenglamasining qiymatlari, chegaraviy natijalarni ifodalaydi, (13), (14) muvozanat tenglamasini va chegaraviy shartlarini quyidagicha sharxlash mumkin:

$\omega=0$ bo‘lsa, u xolda (13) tenglama va unga qo‘yilgan (14) chegaraviy shart quyidagicha bo‘ladi;

ya’ni $k=0$ (1.1-rasmdagi *OM* misol ko‘rinishda).

Yuqoridagi formulamiz quyidagicha ko‘rinishga ega bo‘ladi

$$-2GM_y \frac{d^4 W^{(0)}}{dx^4} \delta W^{(0)} = Q^T \delta W^{(0)} \quad (15)$$

$$2GM_y \frac{d^2 W^{(0)}}{dx^2} \delta \frac{dW^{(0)}}{dx} \Big|_x + 2GM_y \frac{d^3 W^{(0)}}{dx^3} \delta W^{(0)} \Big|_x = Q^T \delta \frac{dW^{(0)}}{dx} \quad (16)$$

2) Agar elastik-plastik va kuchni olishni tasvirlovchi model quydagicha bo'lsa.

(4) formuladan $\omega \neq 0$ bo'lsa, u xolda (12) tenglama va unga qo'yilgan chegaraviy shart quydagicha bo'ladi:

$$-2G \left(M_y - M_y^{\omega(k)} \right) \frac{d^4 W^{(k)}}{dx^4} \delta W^{(k)} = Q^T \delta W^{(k)} + A^{0(k-1)} \quad (17)$$

$$2G \left(M_y - M_y^{\omega(k)} \right) \frac{d^2 W^{(k)}}{dx^2} \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x + 2G \left(M_y - M_y^{\omega(k)} \right) \frac{d^3 W^{(k)}}{dx^3} \delta W^{(k)} \Big|_x = Q^T \delta \frac{dW^{(k)}}{dx} \Big|_x + A^{0(k-1)} \quad (18)$$

Bajarilgan ishi doirasida olib borilgan tadqiqotning maqsadi: balkaning o'zgaruvchan kuchlar ta'siridagi kuchlanganlik- deformatsiyalanganlik holatini A.A.Ilyushin va V.V.Moskvitin nazariyalariga asosan hamda T.Buriyevning ko'rsatmalarini hisobga olgan holda muvozanat tenglamasi keltirib chiqarilgan va unga chekli ayirmalar usuli yordamida ishchi algoritm yaratilgan. Tuzilgan dasturiy ta'minot balkaning tashqi kuchlar ta'sirida kuchlanganlik holatini aniqlash uchun yaratilgan.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR (REFERENCES)

1. M.Olimov, S.Abdujalilov. Matematik va kompyuterli modellashtirish asosiy tushunchalari, 27-29-oktabr, 2021-yil Andijon, O'zbekiston
2. Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education Vol.12 No.10 (2021), 2209-2213 <https://turcomat.org/index.php/turkbilmat/article/view/5277>
3. Abdujalilov S. Matlab dasturi simulink paketi yordamida elektr tokini o'zgarimas holatini identifikasiyalash modelini yaratish erus.uz TASHKENT, UZBEKISTAN 2022/ JUNE 25
4. Problems of Development and Solution of Technological Processes of Cleaning Cotton with Small PJAEE, 17 (7) (2020) Dispersion Particles and Dust
5. S. Adujalilov., S.Parpiyev, «MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH» elektron jurnalining 2021 yil fevralida soni. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6011643>.

6. S.Adujalilov., S.Parpiyev, “INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION 2022/2”.
<http://erus.uz/index.php/ic/article/view/94>
7. Олимов М., Каримов П., Исмоилов Ш. М. К решению краевых задач пространственных стержней при переменных упруго-пластических нагружениях //Молодой ученый. – 2015. – №. 13. – С. 162-167.
8. Olimov M. et al. Mathematical modeling of stress-strain state of loaded rods with account of transverse bending //Bulletin of TUIT: Management and Communication Technologies. – 2018. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 11-22.
9. Олимов М., Исмоилов Ш. М. Solutions of the problem reduced to a fourth-order boundary differential equation with the help of the differential moving method //Проблемы вычислительной и прикладной математики. – 2017. – №. 3. – С. 33-36.
10. Олимов М., Исмоилов Ш. М. Балкани соф эгилишини эластиклик-пластиклик назариясига асосан мувозанат тенгламасини куриш //Научное знание современности. – 2017. – №. 6. – С. 107-111.